

Secrecy-Aware Mobility Control for the ORAN Enabled 6G TN–NTN Continuum

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Abstract—Future wireless network deployments are expected to integrate Terrestrial Network (TN) and Non-Terrestrial Network (NTN) segments to enhance coverage and capacity. However, this convergence also introduces new security challenges for protecting the air interface’s confidentiality. This simulation-based study examines the impact of physical-layer security (PLS) in an integrated TN–NTN architecture under realistic mobility and handover dynamics, using an xApp for control. We extend the scenario to a network with passive downlink eavesdroppers and introduce a secrecy metric to quantify confidentiality in their presence. Simulation results show that the modelled secrecy-aware xApp improves confidentiality against passive downlink eavesdropping by up to 80%, while preserving service quality continuity during the handover. When the xApp decision logic is implemented using an Open Neural Network Exchange (ONNX)-deployed Machine Learning (ML) gating module, the secrecy-outage reduction relative to the non-secrecy baseline reached up to 97.5%. Overall, the results suggest that the unified continuum network should be evaluated not only for coverage extension but also for adaptive security, where the control plane can steer UEs toward serving cells that offer more favourable secrecy conditions under dynamic channel and mobility conditions.

Index Terms—6G, PLS, TN-NTN integration, ONNX-based ML inference, xApp.

I. INTRODUCTION

The convergence of TN and NTN, including satellite and aerial platforms, has become a strategic enabler for delivering ubiquitous, resilient, high-performance connectivity across diverse environments. However, it also increases the threat surface for air-interface confidentiality. Beyond current hybrid approaches, the envisioned TN-NTN continuum requires a tightly integrated network fabric that ensures uninterrupted access, consistent Quality-of-Service (QoS), and security-aware control across heterogeneous infrastructures. This transformation demands close cooperation among Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) and the development of new business and governance models, such as managed multi-tenancy and cross-domain coordination of control and security policies for shared infrastructure. Expanding architectural and protocol designs to include non-satellite flying nodes, such as drones and High-Altitude Platforms (HAPS), creates new opportunities for flexible three-dimensional (3D) network topologies but

also introduces additional adversarial vantage points, highlighting the need for PLS evaluation under dynamic 3D channel conditions. Despite progress in TN–NTN integration and Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) programmability, mobility decisions remain primarily driven by radio Key Performance Indicator (KPI)s (e.g., Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP)/Reference Signal Received Quality (RSRQ)) and do not treat secrecy leakage as a control objective. This leaves a gap where confidentiality can degrade during mobility even when QoS remains acceptable.

Current TN and NTN systems remain operationally fragmented. TNs provide high-capacity coverage in dense areas, whereas NTN extends connectivity to remote and underserved regions. However, secrecy is still not treated as a mobility objective. This paper addresses that gap by studying secrecy-aware mobility control in an O-RAN-enabled TN-NTN scenario. This paper presents a comprehensive vision and technical roadmap for achieving the TN-NTN continuum for secrecy over the air interface at the intersection of O-RAN. The key contributions of this work include:

- 1) Extend a TN–NTN scenario to a network with passive downlink eavesdroppers and incorporate a secrecy-aware Near-Real-Time Radio Intelligent Controller (Near-RT RIC) xApp on top of RSRP-driven mobility.
- 2) Evaluate confidentiality under realistic mobility and handover dynamics, showing how control-plane decisions can reduce secrecy degradation while preserving service continuity (QoS).
- 3) Train a lightweight ML classifier offline from ns-3 time-series traces and deploy it via ONNX for online inference in the Near-RT RIC, enabling probability-based gating of handover evaluation.

The remainder of the paper is organised as follows. Section II reviews TN–NTN integration, O-RAN control, and PLS, and distils the open gap at their intersection. Section III describes the unified service-centric TN-NTN architecture along with its key enablers and interfaces. Section IV presents the simulation setup with a detailed explanation of the designed xApp logic and procedure. Section V evaluates results for secrecy outage, and resulting QoS impact in terms of throughput delay and packet delivery ratio (PDR). Finally, section VI concludes with limitations and future research directions.

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TABLE I: Comparison of Proposed Architecture vs. Existing Standards and Initiatives [1], [2], [3], [4]

Aspect	Existing Standards/Initiatives	Proposed Architecture (This Work)	Differentiation / Novelty
Architecture Scope	Segmented TN-NTN integration with protocol adaptation (3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) Rel-17/18); limited PHY-layer secrecy consideration.	Unified TN-NTN continuum, integrating a PHY-layer secrecy overlay and cross-layer security telemetry.	First End-to-End (E2E) unified TN-NTN architecture that treats secrecy as a KPI, enabling coordinated security across 3D domain.
Control Plane Design	RIC management initiatives primarily optimise RAN performance; security is typically policy-based and not coupled to real-time channel-leakage risk.	Cross-domain control plane that performs mission and secrecy-aware orchestration: handover decisions driven by real-time signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR)/RSRP telemetry and ML model.	Enables joint TN-NTN decisions using a security-risk feedback loop (eavesdropper-aware metrics).
Mobility Handling	Mobility control is typically RSRP/RSRQ-driven; NTN focuses on Doppler/beam tracking, security is not part of handover (HO) trigger logic.	3D-aware mobility and secrecy-aware handover: UAV trajectory/user association can be tuned to reduce secrecy outage (not only to improve coverage).	Using predicted leakage with ML model, reduction improves to 97.5% under dynamic mobility.
Validation	Standards rarely provide open evaluations of secrecy; most work lacks active eavesdropper measurement traces and reproducible PLS benchmarking.	Validated with ns-3 + 5G-LENA + O-RAN emulation for a 20 km ² scenario with 100 UEs and passive EVE nodes, and with an ONNX ML inference module in the control loop to gate HO decisions.	First TN-NTN+O-RAN simulation showing quantified reduced secrecy outage 80%/ with ONNX ML 97.5% reduction together with QoS and HO analysis.

II. RELATED WORK

NTN has progressed from conceptual studies to concrete 5G New Radio (NR) adaptations through 3GPP. Early work in technical report 38.811 [1] examined the impacts of NR on NTN operation, including reference deployment scenarios, channel model adaptations, and the identification of higher-layer and PHY-layer impact areas. Later, consolidated solution directions for NR-NTN, addressing constraints such as large round-trip delay, Doppler, and payload options, and discussing architectural considerations and procedure adaptations for Geostationary Orbit (GSO) and Non-Geostationary Orbit (NGSO) scenarios [5].

In the research community, Space-O-RAN argues that current NTN control planes remain largely monolithic and disconnected from terrestrial orchestration, motivating an O-RAN-inspired programmable control architecture tailored to space constraints, including limited onboard computing, intermittent connectivity, and dynamic topology [6]. A growing body of work demonstrates the utility of xApps for radio optimisation and mobility [7], [8]. Recent studies examine customised conditional handover strategies in O-RAN, and ML-based mobility management to reduce ping-pong effects and handover failures while maintaining throughput [9], [10].

Despite progress related to TN-NTN integration and O-RAN-based mobility and steering xApps, existing RIC-driven mobility solutions [11] predominantly optimise radio KPIs (RSRP/SINR, throughput, load, HO failure) without explicitly accounting for eavesdropping risk or secrecy metrics. Conversely, Recent ns-3 studies have shown that ML-driven handover trigger adaptation can outperform conventional RSRP or distance-based policies by reducing packet loss and improving throughput [12]. However, these approaches optimise only QoS/radio KPIs, and recent research does not incorporate confidentiality risk into the decision loop.

In contrast, our work treats secrecy outage as a gating constraint on mobility actions. PLS studies such as [13]

largely focus on PHY techniques (artificial noise, friendly jamming) under assumed channel knowledge, but they do not operationalise secrecy as a controller KPI that can steer mobility across TN and NTN segments. Our approach complements PHY methods by enabling secrecy-aware steering at the O-RAN control plane. This motivates secrecy-aware xApps that fuse Near-RT measurements from both TN and NTN segments, estimate secrecy outage, and trigger mobility or steering actions to jointly optimise connectivity and confidentiality in integrated TN-NTN deployments. Finally, Table I compares the proposed architecture with existing standards and initiatives.

III. ADAPTATION TO 3D NODES AND NON-SATELLITE NTN

Fig. 1 presents a layered view of a seamless TN/NTN architecture that separates decision-making from domain execution while keeping the data plane simple and efficient. To ensure seamless coexistence and operability with NTN and TN segments, 3D nodes are treated as dynamic, mobile access and relay components: (i) *Logical Abstraction*: Each 3D node is virtualised as a network element with assignable RAN, backhaul, or relay functions, depending on operational needs and platform capabilities. (ii) *Control Plane Anchoring*: Aerial platforms are anchored to the Cross-Segment Control Plane (CSCP), which dynamically assigns roles, functions, and connectivity profiles based on mission objectives and network context. (iii) *Segment Fluidity*: A 3D node may operate as an extension of the terrestrial segment, the NTN segment, or serve as a bridge node facilitating inter-segment traffic routing and handover.

Aerial nodes introduce unique mobility patterns and constraints that must be addressed in control and management logic. Node trajectories, altitude changes, and environmental factors (e.g., wind drift, weather) are modelled to anticipate coverage changes and prevent link disruption. The middle-

Fig. 1: The proposed Service Centric TN-NTN Architecture with secrecy

domain coordination (TN+NTN bridging) layer provides cross-segment coordination by normalising control- and user-plane procedures between the TN and NTN domains. It preserves standard inter-node interfaces (e.g., NG-C/NG-U, Xn-C/Xn-U, X2-C/X2-U) while accounting for NTN-specific impairments such as propagation delay, Doppler, and beam dynamics. This layer enables seamless mobility and traffic steering across heterogeneous access points (terrestrial gNBs, satellites, UAV/HAPS relays) without requiring disruptive changes to the data plane.

The lower Low-PHY/Data Plane executes the configured behaviour via O-DU/O-CU functions and standard RAN protocol layers (MAC/PHY). Fronthaul transport follows common split options (e.g., 7.2x with eCPRI and Ethernet), supporting massive multiple-input and multiple-output (MIMO), edge data centres, and multi-domain connectivity (satellite domain, terrestrial backhaul/midhaul). Measurement reports flow upward via O1/E2/F1 (and associated telemetry paths), while decisions flow downward to enforce mobility, slicing, and secrecy-aware configurations. To explicitly represent confidentiality threats, includes an eavesdropping layer capturing passive, colluding, and mobile eavesdroppers. In our evaluation, these entities serve as an oracle reference for worst-case leakage, since the simulator provides direct eavesdropper-side channel measurements for each candidate cell. More specifically, the secrecy-aware controller can access the strongest eavesdropper observation and therefore evaluate an idealised worst-case leakage condition when making mobility decisions. This

should be interpreted as an upper-bound benchmark on the achievable benefit of secrecy-aware control, rather than as a practically available input. In operational deployments, however, passive eavesdroppers are not directly observable by the network. Therefore, equivalent exposure information would need to be approximated through conservative leakage-risk proxies rather than measured eavesdropper SINR. Such proxies may be derived from geo-risk layers, line-of-sight visibility, terrain and clutter databases, coverage spillover characteristics, or propagation-based worst-case bounds for likely attacker locations. These proxy indicators can then be provided by the Non-RT RIC to support secrecy-aware control decisions in the Near-RT RIC.

IV. SYSTEM MODEL FOR SECRECY AWARE HANDOVER

Fig. 2 shows the simulation system model used throughout the experiment, which combines a TN (Area A) with a NTN (Area B). We consider a hybrid TN-NTN network composed of two disjoint service regions. Area A represents a dense urban terrestrial network (TN) of approximately 4 km^2 (e.g., $2 \text{ km} \times 2 \text{ km}$), served by 10 static 5G gNBs deployed on towers or rooftops. Fifty mobile ground User Equipment (UE)s move within Area A following a random direction mobility pattern. Area B is a rural or remote region of approximately 16 km^2 (e.g., $4 \text{ km} \times 4 \text{ km}$), spatially separated from Area A by an offset along the x -axis. Area B is served by 10 unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV)-mounted gNBs (UAV-BSs) and fifty ground UEs, with altitudes uniformly distributed between 100 and 200 m and mobility confined to the NTN service area. This

setup captures basic 3D deployment effects through aerial node height variation, while more advanced altitude-adaptive trajectory control is left for future work.

Fig. 2: Simulation System Model

In our implementation, the carrier operates in the mid-band with $B = 20$ MHz per cell, using a downlink center frequency of approximately 4.0 GHz and an uplink center frequency of approximately 3.9 GHz. Radio propagation is modelled in a macrocellular scenario (e.g., UMa for TN and RMa for NTN) with fading enabled. We focus on access-side effects, with the backhaul abstracted via the 5G-LENA Evolved Packet Core (EPC) using a high-capacity P2P link between the Packet Data Gateway (P-GW) and the remote host (e.g., 10 Gb/s and negligible delay) to avoid bottlenecks outside the Radio Access Network (RAN). The employed 5G-LENA release is compatible with an O-RAN Split 7.2x-style functional decomposition, and our scenario integrates a Near-RT RIC loop for measurement collection and optional handover control. All simulations were performed on a system running Ubuntu 24.04.2 LTS (noble) using g++ 13.3.0 on an x86_64 architecture.

The network operates under an ORAN-compliant architecture, and each UE and gNB hosts an E2 node terminator that periodically reports measurements to the RIC via a set of reporters (e.g., location, serving cell, RSRP, SINR, and application-layer loss). The RIC queries a data repository (SQLite-backed in our implementation) and runs a custom Logic Module (LM) for mobility management at a configurable decision interval (e.g., every 2 s). To avoid conflicts between native handover logic and RIC-issued commands, the underlying NR handover algorithm is set to "NrNoOpHandoverAlgorithm" when the LM xapp controls handovers.

A. Physical Layer Secrecy

Each UE continuously measures the downlink from nearby gNBs/UAV-BSs. The key measurements used by the RIC are

RSRP and downlink SINR. We model 6 passive eavesdroppers (three in each area) as NR-capable receiver nodes that do not generate application traffic. In ns-3, these eavesdroppers are instantiated as UE devices to produce the same PHY layer measurements (RSRP/SINR) as legitimate UEs. They only "listen" and report channel quality; they do not introduce interference. The RIC records eavesdropper SINR per cell and uses the worst-case eavesdropper (maximum SINR among all eavesdroppers for a given cell) to evaluate leakage risk. In this work, passive eavesdroppers are modelled as receiver nodes that report RSRP/SINR to enable computation of the secrecy metric. This provides an upper-bound benchmark for secrecy-aware mobility control.

We employ standard PLS metrics based on the wiretap model. Let $\gamma_b(t)$ denote the legitimate UE downlink SINR (linear scale) on the serving link and let $\gamma_e(t)$ denote the *maximum* eavesdropper SINR among all eavesdroppers that can observe the same transmission. The instantaneous spectral efficiencies (in bits/s/Hz) are:

$$C_b(t) = \log_2(1 + \gamma_b(t)), \quad C_e(t) = \log_2(1 + \gamma_e(t)) \quad (1)$$

The instantaneous secrecy capacity (bits/s/Hz) is

$$C_s(t) = [C_b(t) - C_e(t)]^+ = \max\{C_b(t) - C_e(t), 0\} \quad (2)$$

The average secrecy rate for a UE is $\bar{C}_s = \mathbb{E}[C_s(t)]$. Given a target secrecy rate R_{sec} (bits/s/Hz), secrecy outage probability (SOP) is:

$$P_{\text{out}} = \Pr\{C_s(t) < R_{\text{sec}}\} \quad (3)$$

We also report the fraction of time with strictly positive secrecy ($\Pr\{C_s(t) > 0.1\}$) and secure coverage, defined as the fraction of UEs that satisfy $C_s(t) > 0$ (or $C_s(t) \geq R_{\text{sec}}$) for at least a chosen percentage of the simulation time (e.g., 95%), enabling spatial secrecy maps. The remaining 5% is required for the startup and shutdown of the applications.

B. Secrecy-Aware Handover Logic Module (xApp)

The key algorithm is a near-RT RIC logic module LM that makes HO decisions by combining traditional RSRP-based mobility with a secrecy constraint. Intuitively, the LM recommends HO to a neighbour cell only if the neighbour provides a sufficiently stronger signal and the predicted secrecy capacity is above a target threshold. Let P_{serv} and P_{cand} denote the measured RSRP (dBm) of the serving and candidate cells. A candidate is considered for handover only if the RSRP gain exceeds a hysteresis/threshold margin (e.g., $\Delta > 2$ dB), which mitigates ping-pong effects.

$$\Delta \triangleq P_{\text{cand}} - P_{\text{serv}} \quad (4)$$

For each candidate cell that passes the RSRP gate, the LM requires an estimate of the legitimate-link SINR on that candidate cell. In practice, UEs typically do not have instantaneous downlink data-channel SINR measurements for neighbouring cells, because they are not scheduled on or decoding the candidate cell's PDSCH at the time of decision. Instead, the measurement repository primarily provides the

current serving-cell downlink SINR together with neighbour-cell signal-strength indicators such as RSRP. Therefore, in the absence of per-neighbour downlink data-channel SINR, we use a lightweight control-oriented proxy for candidate-link quality. Let γ_{serv} denote the UE's current serving-cell downlink SINR (linear scale). The candidate-link SINR is approximated by scaling the serving-link SINR according to the RSRP gain:

$$\hat{\gamma}_{\text{cand}} \approx \gamma_{\text{serv}} \cdot 10^{\Delta/10}, \quad (5)$$

Equation (5) interpreted as a lightweight candidate-link quality proxy rather than as an exact post-handover SINR prediction. It captures the first-order effect of large-scale signal-strength improvement through the RSRP difference, but it does not require explicitly modelling channel conditions (e.g. candidate-cell interference, scheduler allocation, beamforming differences, instantaneous cell load, or fast-fading mismatch between the serving and candidate links at the xApp). In the ns-3/5G-LENA implementation, the realised UE and eavesdropper SINRs are obtained directly from PHY-layer DIDataSnr/DICtrlSnr measurements, which already reflect the channel conditions. Accordingly, the secrecy results reported in the evaluation are computed from measured SINR traces on the realised serving cell after mobility decisions, whereas (5) is used only to rank or gate candidate cells at decision time.

The LM then estimates the eavesdropper SINR for the same candidate cell by taking the maximum over all eavesdropper measurements reported to the RIC:

$$\hat{\gamma}_e(\text{cand}) = \max_{k \in \mathcal{E}} \gamma_{e,k}(\text{cand}), \quad (6)$$

where \mathcal{E} is the set of eavesdroppers. If no recent eavesdropper measurement is available for that candidate cell, the LM uses a conservative fallback value (e.g., -5 dB) so that handover can proceed without interruption. The predicted secrecy capacity for the candidate cell is:

$$\hat{C}_s(\text{cand}) = [\log_2(1 + \hat{\gamma}_{\text{cand}}) - \log_2(1 + \hat{\gamma}_e(\text{cand}))]^+. \quad (7)$$

A candidate is accepted only if $\hat{C}_s(\text{cand}) \geq R_{\text{sec}}$, where R_{sec} is the target secrecy rate (e.g., 0.1 bits/s/Hz). At each near-RT RIC decision interval (e.g., 2s), the logic module (LM) processes each UE by first fetching the latest UE state from the data repository, including the serving cell ID, and the most recent RSRP measurements for the serving and neighbouring cells, along with the latest serving cell downlink SINR. Next, the LM applies stability constraints to avoid excessive handovers: it ignores handover decisions during an initial warm up period (e.g., the first 2 s), enforces a minimum inter handover time per UE (e.g., 2 s), and blocks new commands if a previous handover remains pending until a timeout expires (e.g., 2 s). After these checks, the LM evaluates candidate neighbour cells by sorting them in descending order of measured RSRP P_{cand} and testing each candidate sequentially.

A candidate is considered only if its RSRP gain over the serving cell exceeds a hysteresis margin, i.e., $\Delta = P_{\text{cand}} - P_{\text{serv}} > 2$ dB. For each remaining candidate, the LM predicts the UE SINR on that candidate cell using (5), retrieves the

worst-case eavesdropper SINR $\hat{\gamma}_e(\text{cand})$ for the same cell from eavesdropper reports, and computes the predicted secrecy capacity $\hat{C}_s(\text{cand})$ using (7). The first candidate (highest RSRP order) that satisfies both the RSRP gain gate and the secrecy constraint $\hat{C}_s(\text{cand}) \geq R_{\text{sec}}$ is selected as the handover target, after which the LM issues a command containing the UE identifier and the target cell ID; if no candidate passes, the UE remains on its current serving cell. The secrecy-aware mobility objective is to maintain a channel advantage for the legitimate UE over the strongest eavesdropper in the serving cell. If a candidate cell offers higher signal quality but also results in a high eavesdropper SINR, the secrecy gate vetoes that handover to prevent a secrecy outage.

In operational deployments, the eavesdropper SINR is not directly observable; therefore, $\hat{\gamma}_e$ is interpreted as a leakage-risk estimate derived from conservative propagation bounds and cell-level risk maps, rather than from a measured eavesdropper channel. We assume that the Non-RT RIC computes a per-cell exposure score (riskScore $\in [0, 1]$) from operator knowledge and geo-context and provides these indicators to the Near-RT RIC. The Near-RT RIC (via the proposed xApp) then maps the risk-score to a conservative leakage proxy $\hat{\gamma}_e$ for each candidate cell (e.g., by interpolating between low-risk and high-risk attacker SINR bounds), and uses this proxy to gate or rank handover decisions. In this study, we used passive receivers (eaves) in the simulator to benchmark secrecy-aware steering under an oracle-leakage model, where $\hat{\gamma}_e$ is set to the measured worst-case eve SINR per candidate cell. This oracle case provides an upper bound on the achievable gains when knowledge of the leakage is available.

C. ONNX-based ML Trigger Gate for Secrecy-Aware Handover

To mitigate unnecessary handover attempts and the resulting oscillations and signalling overhead, we augment the proposed secrecy-aware xApp with a lightweight ML trigger gate that predicts whether a UE is likely to perform a handover in the next Near-RT RIC control interval. The ML component does not replace the secrecy-aware target selection logic; instead, it determines when HO evaluation should be executed, where there are no secrecy outages. The classifier is trained offline using traces collected at each management interval Δ . For every UE, we log the serving cell identifier along with secrecy-relevant indicators: the legitimate downlink SINR γ_b , the Eve SINR estimate γ_e (according to the configured leakage model), and the resulting secrecy capacity C_s . Supervised labels are derived from serving-cell changes between consecutive decision ticks:

$$\text{HO}_{\text{next}}(t) = \mathbb{1}\{\text{cell}(t + \Delta) \neq \text{cell}(t)\}. \quad (8)$$

This yields a binary classification dataset aligned with the Near-RT RIC control (one sample per UE per decision instant). To avoid train leakage across UEs, we perform grouped splitting by UE identifier. We employ a gradient boosted tree classifier with probabilistic output $P(\text{HO}_{\text{next}}) \in [0, 1]$ and

export the trained model to ONNX for deployment in the Near-RT RIC runtime. For online inference, the ONNX model is loaded by the Near-RT RIC logic module "OranLmNrOnnxSecrecyAwareHandover". At each LM execution tick and for each UE, the module retrieves (i) the serving-link SINR from the data repository, (ii) the corresponding leakage SINR according to the selected leakage model, and then (iii) computes C_s and forms the same feature vector used in training. The feature vector captures the current secrecy state, one-step history, and short-term dynamics:

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = [\gamma_b^{\text{dB}}(t), \gamma_e^{\text{dB}}(t), C_s(t), \mathbb{1}\{C_s(t) < C_{s,\text{min}}\}, \\ \gamma_b^{\text{dB}}(t - \Delta), C_s(t - \Delta), \mathbb{1}\{C_s(t - \Delta) < C_{s,\text{min}}\}, \\ \Delta\gamma_b^{\text{dB}}(t), \Delta C_s(t)], \quad (9)$$

where $\Delta\gamma_b^{\text{dB}}(t) = \gamma_b^{\text{dB}}(t) - \gamma_b^{\text{dB}}(t - \Delta)$ and $\Delta C_s(t) = C_s(t) - C_s(t - \Delta)$. The one-step values are obtained from the cached previous tick state; consequently, the trigger gate becomes active once the previous-step features are available.

The model output is used to decide whether to run the HO evaluation in the current interval. Specifically, the HO evaluation is executed only if

$$P(\text{HO}_{\text{next}}) \geq \tau_{\text{HO}}, \quad (10)$$

where τ_{HO} is a configurable threshold. If (10) does not hold, the LM suppresses HO evaluation for that UE and keeps the serving cell unchanged, reducing spurious HO triggers under short-term fluctuations. If (10) holds, the LM proceeds with the full secrecy-aware target selection logic. To preserve security responsiveness, the ML trigger gate is disabled when the UE is already in secrecy outage ($C_s < C_{s,\text{min}}$). In that case, the LM prioritizes secrecy recovery and evaluates candidate cells regardless of $P(\text{HO}_{\text{next}})$.

In aggregate, using the model-per-UE decision-tick dataset, we trained and validated a scikit-learn classifier to estimate the probability of an imminent handover. That trained model was exported to ONNX to enable lightweight, framework-agnostic inference within the Near-RT RIC runtime. We then integrated ONNX Runtime into the ns-3 logic module OranLmNrOnnxSecrecyAwareHandover, which loads separate TN-NTN models and performs online inference at each LM execution tick. In operation, the ML output acts only as a trigger gate, while the secrecy-aware handover procedure remains responsible for target selection by applying RSRP, hysteresis constraints, and secrecy-capacity checks, with a dedicated outage mode that prioritises secrecy recovery. When a handover is selected, the LM issues an NR-to-NR handover command via OranCommandNr2NrHandover. If the ONNX model is unavailable (e.g., not loaded), the module reverts to the baseline secrecy-aware behavior without gating, thereby ensuring robust operation.

V. NUMERICAL RESULTS

Fig. 3a reports the per-UE downlink throughput over time for the TN-NTN O-RAN scenario, without secrecy against the

one with secrecy. After traffic starts ($t \approx 2$ s), both configurations quickly stabilise at ≈ 0.25 – 0.28 Mbps/UE and remain closely overlapped for most of the run, indicating that enabling secrecy awareness has only a minor impact on throughput in this setup. This limited difference is expected given the scenario parameters: each UE is offered user datagram protocol (UDP) on-off traffic at 1 Mbps with 1500 B packets and randomized on/off periods [Uniform(0.1, 0.5) s], while the air interface is shared (20 MHz NR carrier at ~ 4 GHz, orthogonal frequency division multiple access (OFDMA) with proportional fair (PF) scheduling, fixed Tx powers of 38 dBm at gNB and 23 dBm at UE, and mobility in both TN and NTN regions). In our implementation, the secrecy mechanism does not modify the PHY/MAC (no extra redundancy, artificial noise, or power backoff), so the scheduler and resource grid largely dominate the achieved throughput. Finally, the sharp drop to zero throughput after $t \approx 35$ s is consistent with the application stop time in the simulation.

Fig. 3b shows the average E2E packet delay per UE over time for the same TN-NTN O-RAN scenario, the curves represent the central tendency across all UEs remain stable around ≈ 0.115 – 0.120 s while the shaded bands indicate the spread across the user population, reflecting heterogeneity between favourable radio conditions and more challenging conditions. This outcome is consistent with the design of the proposed secrecy overlay: the xApp LM affects based on SINR-derived secrecy (C_s) evaluated every management_interval ≈ 2 s with a freshness constraint (maxAge ≈ 1 s), while the underlying NR protocol stack (MAC scheduling, HARQ behavior as configured, numerology/resource grid, and EPC transport delay) is unchanged. Thus, delay is primarily governed by OFDMA-PF airtime sharing and short-term buffering from bursty UDP on-off arrivals. The small late-run deviation at $t \approx 33$ – 35 s is likely an artefact of end-of-traffic sampling rather than a persistent secrecy-induced effect. Overall, secrecy-aware HO adds confidentiality awareness with negligible E2E latency impact for the considered TN-NTN O-RAN and NR setting.

Fig. 3c shows the per-UE PDR over time. Both schemes closely overlap at around ≈ 60 – 65% for most of the experiment, indicating that secrecy-aware control does not materially affect PDR reliability. This is expected since secrecy is introduced only in the handover decision logic, while the NR PHY/MAC operation remains unchanged. Accordingly, PDR is dominated in both cases by bursty UDP on-off traffic, shared-airtime scheduling over the 20 MHz NR channel, and mobility-related fading, interference, and transient queueing. The slight late-time deviation is best explained by windowed PDR variability and handover dynamics, not by a systematic secrecy-induced loss process. The relatively modest PDR level mainly stems from disabled downlink HARQ retransmissions and unrecovered losses under mobility and channel variation.

Fig. 4 shows that the secrecy-enabled RSRP handover-based xApp consistently reduces the secrecy outage probability compared to the baseline without a secrecy-integrated logic

Fig. 3: UE quality of service comparison under TN-NTN-ORAN with and without secrecy at time t seconds: (a) throughput distribution, (b) delay distribution, (c) PDR distribution.

module. At each sampling time t , the metric is computed as $P_{\text{out}}^{\text{HO}}(t) = N_{\text{HO} \cap \text{out}}(t) / N_{\text{UE}}(t)$, where $N_{\text{UE}}(t)$ is the total number of UE samples at time t across TN and NTN, and $N_{\text{HO} \cap \text{out}}(t)$ counts only UEs that both change serving cell relative to the previous sample (handover) within the same domain (TN or NTN) and are flagged as outage ($\text{outage} = 1$) at that handover instant. The secrecy-enabled approach reduces the mean handover-triggered outage probability by approximately 80% relative to the baseline over 1500 test samples (at time t from 50 UEs, we obtain 50 samples). With the ONNX-ML gated controller, the average per-time handover-triggered outage probability further decreases, yielding around a 97.5% reduction relative to the non-secrecy baseline. These results indicate that enabling secrecy significantly improves robustness to outage events during mobility transitions in the TN-NTN-ORAN secrecy-integrated network.

to increased contention and more frequent transient service disruptions during handover execution. This observation confirms that, even with secrecy enabled, system robustness during mobility transitions is sensitive to offered load, and higher UE density increases the probability of handover-associated secrecy outages.

However, incorporating the ONNX-based ML gate further stabilises the outage period; the ONNX curves remain near zero for most timestamps and exhibit only small, isolated excursions, whereas the rule-based secrecy xApp shows larger and more frequent spikes. This indicates that the learned ML gate suppresses secrecy-degrading handovers more consistently, reducing both the amplitude and variability of $P_{\text{out}}^{\text{HO}}(t)$ under both load settings, with the clearest stable effect in the higher-load 150-UE case.

Fig. 4: Comparison of handover-triggered secrecy outage probability for the integrated TN-NTN-ORAN without secrecy, with secrecy (baseline), and with secrecy (ONNX-ML) for 100 UEs

Fig. 5 compares the handover-related secrecy outage probability for two offered-load settings: a total of 150 UEs (75 TN + 75 NTN) and a total of 100 UEs (50 TN + 50 NTN). Overall, the baseline model 150-UE configuration exhibits a higher and more sustained $P_{\text{out}}^{\text{HO}}(t)$ during several time intervals, indicating that increased load amplifies the likelihood of secrecy outage coinciding with mobility transitions, due

Fig. 5: Comparison of secrecy outage probability for the integrated TN-NTN-ORAN with secrecy (baseline), and with secrecy (ONNX-ML) for 100 UEs and 150 UEs

Fig. 6 plots the SOP over all UE samples from both TN and NTN using the concatenation mode (TN+NTN samples are merged and weighted by their row counts). SOP increases monotonically with R_{sec} , since more stringent secrecy-rate targets are harder to satisfy under mobility, fading, and interference. At the operating point $R_{\text{sec}} = 0.1$ bits/s/Hz, the baseline without secrecy exhibits $P_{\text{out}} = 0.2783$ (computed over 1750 samples; TN=800, NTN=950). Introducing the secrecy-aware xApp reduces the outage to 0.2442 (over 1900

Fig. 6: Secrecy outage probability versus target secrecy rate

samples; $TN=950$, $NTN=950$), while the secrecy+ONNX ML gate yields the lowest outage of 0.2328 (over 1800 samples; $TN=850$, $NTN=950$). Relative to the baseline, these reductions indicate that secrecy-aware mobility control shifts the C_s distribution toward higher values, thereby decreasing the fraction of samples that fall below the target secrecy rate. The gap between the secrecy xApp and the ONNX-gated approach is comparatively the same in this figure because the metric is computed over all samples, most of which correspond to steady-state periods, and no handover samples are included. In our design, the ONNX gate primarily influences HO acceptance/rejection decisions; therefore, its largest impact is concentrated around mobility-trigger instants, while the overall C_s distribution aggregated over all time samples is only mildly perturbed. Nevertheless, the consistently lower curve achieved by the ONNX-gated scheme indicates that learning-based gating further suppresses low- C_s events beyond the rule-based secrecy xApp, thereby improving secrecy reliability across the TN-NTN system.

Based on the above results, we conclude that the secrecy-aware Near-RT RIC xApp improves confidentiality during mobility while leaving user-plane performance largely unchanged. In particular, ONNX-ML secrecy-gated handover decisions reduce SOP by about 97.5% reduction relative to the non-secrecy case, confirming a consistent secrecy-reliability gain across the evaluated load settings. A key limitation of the present study is that leakage knowledge is provided by passive receiver nodes in simulation, which yields oracle-like eavesdropper information and therefore an upper-bound estimate of achievable secrecy-aware steering gains.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper examined PLS in integrated TN-NTN networks under realistic mobility and handover conditions. By extending an ns-3 TN-NTN scenario with passive eavesdroppers and introducing secrecy-aware metrics, we showed that conventional RSRP-based handover is insufficient when confidentiality is a concern. The proposed O-RAN Near-RT RIC xApp augments traditional mobility decisions with a secrecy-aware gate and SINR prediction, enabling the network to steer UEs toward

cells offering better secrecy conditions. Results indicate that this approach improves confidentiality against passive eavesdropping by reducing handover-associated secrecy outage. These findings highlight the importance of considering adaptive security, along with coverage and capacity, in the design of TN-NTN systems. Extending the altitude range and analysing how to mitigate the resulting degradation in secrecy and connectivity through risk-aware steering, or adaptive trajectory control, are left for future work. And we will explore more realistic adversary models, richer 3D mobility scenarios, and the integration of additional PLS techniques with load-aware and advanced learning-based decision mechanisms to further enhance secrecy in dynamic TN-NTN environments.

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